

Scientific Lake

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Deliverable D6.2: Communication, engagement, and exploitation report

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Abstract

Deliverable D6.2 reports SciLake's Communication, Engagement, Dissemination, and Exploitation work. It describes how SciLake refined its narrative and channels (the website and partner and community networks) and summarises outputs and reach, including communication assets and scientific publications. It also reviews stakeholder engagement and lessons learned, and outlines exploitation and sustainability planning supported by the Horizon Booster go-to-market programme. It identifies two Key Exploitable Results: (KER1) the Scientific Lake Toolkit and (KER2) interoperable Scientific Knowledge Graph datasets published on Zenodo using the shared SKG-IF format, alongside an assessment of impacts, risks, challenges, and mitigation measures.

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Abbreviation List

- AI** – Artificial Intelligence
- API** – Application Programming Interface
- CCAM** – Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility
- CC-BY** – Creative Commons Attribution license
- CLL** - Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia
- CoARA** – Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
- DOI** – Digital Object Identifier
- DORI** – Declaration on Open Research Information
- DSR** – Document Structure Recognition (tool)
- ECEMF** – European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum
- EOSC** – European Open Science Cloud
- ESFRIs** – European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
- EU** – European Union
- G2M** – Go-to-market
- KER** – Key Exploitable Result
- KPI** – Key Performance Indicator
- NLP** – Natural Language Processing
- RDA** – Research Data Alliance
- SDGs** – Sustainable Development Goals
- SKG** – Scientific Knowledge Graph
- SKG-IF** – Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework
- SMEs** – Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
- UVP** – Unique Value Proposition

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable reports the strategy, implementation, and outcomes of SciLake's Communication, Engagement and Exploitation work over the full project lifetime, and reports on the outcomes achieved at project closure. It builds on the Communication, Engagement and Dissemination Plan that was defined in Month 6 (Deliverable D6.1, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14499382](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14499382)) and provides a consolidated report of how SciLake's narrative, stakeholder messaging, channels, and engagement pathways evolved as project results matured.

Over the project, SciLake refined its key messages to address a core challenge: scientific knowledge is increasingly abundant yet fragmented across heterogeneous sources, limiting discovery, reuse, and evidence-based decision-making. SciLake's value proposition is to help communities transform fragmented domain knowledge into standardised, interoperable Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) and to build value-added services on top of them, through close collaboration between technical experts and domain specialists across four disciplines (neuroscience, cancer, transportation, and energy).

Communication and dissemination actions were implemented through a coherent platform centred on the project website (<https://scilake.eu/>) and extended through partner and community channels. Across the project, SciLake reached 8,378 users and ~26,000 page views on the website; published 40 website news items; issued six newsletter editions; produced and distributed printed materials (100 factsheets/cards; 80 stickers) and maintained a dissemination toolkit (visual identity, factsheet, postcard, poster, infographics, and slide deck). SciLake also released five pilot-specific press releases and sustained scientific dissemination through 6 journal articles, 12 conference/workshop proceedings, and one contribution to a periodic magazine, with outputs deposited in open repositories and cross-linked from the website.

Engagement activities focused on moving stakeholders from awareness to reuse by meeting communities in relevant venues. In total, SciLake partners contributed to 40 external events, complemented by SciLake-led and co-organised initiatives, including the OSFAIR 2023 workshop on Open Science Knowledge Graphs (150 participants), SciLake plenary meetings (50 participants), the EOSC Symposium 2024 unconference session on interoperability (60 participants), a domain workshop on FAIRness and transparency in transport research (15 participants), and the final online showcase "From fragments to insights" (74 participants). Over the project, SciLake adjusted its communication channels by relying more on partner

and community networks and interactive events, rather than broad social media campaigns, based on what worked best for its specialised audiences.

With support from the Horizon Booster go-to-market programme, SciLake outlined exploitation outcomes and sustainability pathways and identified two Key Exploitable Results (KERs):

- Scientific Lake Toolkit (KER1): a modular, openly accessible bundle of 14 interoperable resources (open data, tools, and services) supporting knowledge extraction, integration, discovery, impact analysis, and reproducibility-oriented use cases. The toolkit is made available via the D4Science data catalogue (https://services.d4science.org/catalogue-d4s?path=/organization/scilake_lab) and is designed to onboard additional providers adhering to shared interoperability principles.
- SKG dataset collection (KER2): five interoperable SKG datasets produced in SciLake's pilot domains (neuroscience, cancer, energy, maritime transport, and CCAM transport), published on Zenodo with persistent identifiers and clear licensing, and created using the Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) representation format, which ensures a common, standards-based structure so the datasets can be reused across services.

The report is organised as follows: Section 2 describes the methodology; Section 3 summarises SciLake's key messages; Sections 4 and 5 report communication and engagement activities; and Section 6 details the exploitation strategy and plan for KER1 (Scientific Lake Toolkit) and KER2 (SKG dataset collection), with supporting exploitation material in the Appendix; and Section 7 assesses the impact, risks, challenges, and mitigation measures for communication, engagement, and exploitation.

2. Methodology

This final report describes the implementation and results of SciLake's Communication, Engagement, and Exploitation work at the end of the project. Its objective is to provide an evidence-based account of how the strategy defined in Month 6 was implemented and adapted over time, and to summarise the outcomes achieved in terms of reach, engagement, uptake, exploitation, and the sustainability of project results.

Quantitative indicators were collected through the project's ongoing monitoring of communication and dissemination. These included website analytics, newsletter and social media metrics, and the number of news items, press releases, and other dissemination materials. Qualitative and activity-based evidence was also gathered through partners'

structured reporting forms, which documented contributions to communication, dissemination, and engagement activities such as events, presentations, publications, datasets, and collaborations.

To that end, the report synthesises the activities carried out throughout the project to engage the identified communities, showing how key messages were tailored and how results were promoted to support adoption. The approach followed a multi-phase implementation, with phases running in parallel, based on:

(i) refining key messages to clearly articulate SciLake's value proposition for relevant stakeholder groups (Sec. 3);

(ii) deploying coherent communication materials to maximise visibility and promote reuse of SciLake outputs (Sec. 4);

(iii) identifying and prioritising the most relevant dissemination and engagement opportunities as results emerged. In practice, we combined outreach at external venues with SciLake-led events to support dialogue and uptake. First, we met stakeholders in their "natural" settings by bringing SciLake results to thematic venues through paper presentations, lightning talks, posters, and other conference contributions. In parallel, we proactively organised dedicated initiatives to foster dialogue and uptake by convening workshops and panel discussions, both as SciLake-led events and in synergy with other INFRAEOSC projects, as well as at broader open science conferences (Sec. 5).

(iv) receiving professional mentorship to strengthen the project's exploitation approach beyond its duration, by participating in the go-to-market module of the Horizon Booster program. The programme helped partners identify KERs, align exploitation intentions, and run market and value analyses using standard canvases. The results were packaged into an exploitation strategy for each KER, including a short description, a roadmap with actions, responsibilities, and timing, and a risk map with key risks and mitigation measures (Sec. 6).

3. SciLake's key messages

This chapter presents SciLake's core narrative (3.1) and clear messages for different stakeholders (3.2). It summarises the problem SciLake addresses, the value delivered through interoperable Scientific Knowledge Graphs and value-added services, and how this proposition is tailored to different audiences to support awareness, engagement, and uptake of the project results.

3.1 Core Narrative

SciLake's core narrative addresses a central challenge in today's research landscape: scientific knowledge is increasingly abundant yet fragmented across heterogeneous sources, making it difficult to connect and reuse at scale. This fragmentation hinders discovery and limits the ability of researchers, infrastructures, and other stakeholders to extract reliable insights that support evidence-based decision-making.

SciLake addresses this problem by providing an environment that helps communities **transform fragmented domain knowledge into standardized, interoperable Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) and to build value-added services on top of them**, that can support day-to-day research workflows and broader goals such as knowledge discovery and research reproducibility. This is illustrated in the visual asset in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Why SciLake: turning fragmented scientific information into interoperable Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) to enable discovery, reuse, and value-added services.

A key aspect of the narrative is why this transformation is difficult to achieve in practice. Domain experts typically possess the contextual understanding needed to model and validate knowledge accurately, but they may lack the specialised technical expertise required to implement SKG workflows independently. Conversely, knowledge management and technical

experts can provide methods and tooling, but without deep domain input, they risk producing representations that are misaligned with disciplinary practices and real research questions. SciLake's approach is therefore built on **collaboration between partners with expertise in knowledge management and domain experts from four disciplines (neuroscience, cancer, transportation, and energy) to co-design and validate SKG-driven services grounded in real-world use cases.**

This narrative was consistently reflected across SciLake's communication platform and dissemination materials. The project website and visual assets were aligned to communicate the same storyline: moving "from fragmented data to knowledge graphs," an ecosystem where knowledge can be created, interlinked, and maintained. Visually, this was reinforced by the ecosystem representation, which made the project structure and its tiers immediately understandable, as shown in Figure 2.

***Figure 2:** SciLake Ecosystem: the two-tier model combining the foundational Scientific Lake Service with discipline-specific value-added services.*

Within this framing, SciLake introduced the concept of the **open Scientific Lake**: a set of components designed to support easy data access, improved knowledge discovery, and research-related activities such as reproducibility-oriented workflows. The ecosystem is presented as a two-tier model. At its heart lies the Scientific Lake Service: the foundational tier that provides core components for creating, interlinking, and maintaining domain-specific SKGs, enabling seamless access and querying of large volumes of scientific information. Building on this, the value-added services tier delivers discipline-specific applications and services that help communities explore their domains more effectively.

Finally, the narrative is grounded through the project's **Research Community Pilots**. By actively involving domain experts in design and feedback loops around early prototypes, SciLake ensured that the resulting services are configurable, adaptable, and relevant to large research communities.

3.2 Stakeholder value propositions

Stakeholder messaging was developed to translate SciLake's overall narrative into concise, audience-specific value propositions. While the project's core promise remained consistent (supporting communities in creating and using interoperable Scientific Knowledge Graphs and related services), the emphasis was adapted to reflect each group's context. This mapping clarified the concrete benefits for each audience, guided the selection of the most relevant dissemination and engagement venues, and informed targeted calls to collaborate. Building on this approach, Sections 4, 5, and 6 report SciLake's activities and specify the stakeholder groups addressed.

Table 1 summarises SciLake's tailored messaging for the main stakeholder groups and highlights the specific benefits for each audience. These messages were included in the SciLake factsheet and disseminated through the project channels, including as printed material at conferences and stakeholder-facing events.

Table 1: SciLake's tailored messaging for key stakeholder groups.

Stakeholder group	Key message
Researchers	SciLake supports researchers in creating, managing, accessing, and processing scholarly content to enhance the visibility and value of research outputs.
Builders and operators of thematic or national SKGs <i>EOSC providers</i>	SciLake increases the offer of community-driven SKGs, improves the interlinking of SKGs and scholarly content through its tools and services, providing an easy, transparent, and effective management of scholarly content.
Computer Science Communities <i>Big data, graph, AI, NLP, experts of metadata standards</i>	SciLake improves the quality of SKGs in terms of disambiguation, enrichment, impact, and reproducibility assessment functions.
Impact assessment experts <i>Research communities, SMEs</i>	SciLake offers a multi-perspective analysis of impact metrics and indicators. It brings transparency in assessment exercises via the proliferation of open data and tools.
Research administrators and policy makers	SciLake enables the identification of research objects and research trends, and the effective assessment and tracking of the reproducibility of research outputs.
General public	SciLake amplifies valuable, credible research through scientific communication.

4. Communication activities

This chapter summarises how SciLake implemented communication across the project lifetime, covering objectives, assets produced, distribution channels, and measurable results.

SciLake's communication work aimed to move stakeholders from awareness of the project to the reuse of its results. Activities followed a consistent narrative and visual identity, with the project website as the main hub and partner/community channels extending the project's reach. The approach combined recurring actions (e.g., newsletters and INFRAEOSC communications) with targeted dissemination at high-relevance venues, including thematic and open-science conferences.

Dissemination toolkit

SciLake produced and maintained a dissemination toolkit to ensure consistent representation across partners, channels, and events. The toolkit is available at <https://scilake.eu/dissemination-toolkit> and includes:

- Visual identity (logo and related graphic assets)
- Two-sided postcard (project overview and key messages)
- Factsheet (objectives, stakeholder-oriented value proposition, and key results)
- Poster (high-level project overview)

Additional materials were shared within the consortium and reused in public presentations, including an introductory slide deck and the infographics supporting the "Why SciLake" narrative and the ecosystem overview (Figures 1–2), also shown on the project home page.

Website and online communication

SciLake maintained the project website as the central access point for up-to-date information and access to project results (<https://scilake.eu/>). Website content was updated iteratively as outputs matured. In the early phase, it focused on project objectives, consortium information, and the core narrative; in the mid-to-late phase, it was expanded with results-oriented sections and engagement opportunities. Targeted updates were made to the Services page (<https://scilake.eu/services>) and Case Studies page (<https://scilake.eu/case-studies>) following the publication of the corresponding deliverables, and additional pages were created to support uptake, including Collaborations (<https://scilake.eu/collaborations>) and Training blog (<https://scilake.eu/training-blog>).

In parallel, SciLake published regular website news items and partner news posts announcing major releases and event highlights (<https://scilake.eu/news>). A set of five pilot-specific press releases was disseminated via SciLake and partner channels (including OpenAIRE, HES-SO, EBRAINS, ICCS, CERTH, and KI) and collected on the Press page: <https://scilake.eu/press>. SciLake also issued a newsletter twice per year.

Regarding social media, SciLake maintained an X (Twitter) account: https://x.com/SciLake_project. Overall, engagement through this platform proved less impactful than initially anticipated, especially after the transition from Twitter to X. In response, SciLake adopted a more targeted dissemination strategy, prioritising established community channels (e.g. OpenAIRE networks, EOSC-related initiatives, and partner organisations) and direct interaction through events and workshops. The X account was kept active, while partner amplification and community channels (including organisational websites, mailing lists, and community groups) were increasingly used to extend reach.

Scientific dissemination

SciLake supported scientific and technical dissemination through peer-reviewed journal articles and conference proceedings, complemented by conference and workshop contributions (presentations and posters). To maximise discoverability and reuse, each output category was deposited in an appropriate open repository and cross-linked from the project website: papers are collected on the Publications page (<https://scilake.eu/publications>); datasets are shared via Zenodo (SciLake community: https://zenodo.org/communities/scilake_project/); and software is released through open code and model repositories, primarily GitHub and Hugging Face. Project public deliverable reports and event presentation materials are also made available via the SciLake Zenodo community.

Key Performance Indicators

Table 2 summarises the key performance indicators (KPIs) for SciLake's dissemination and communication activities throughout the project. For a complete record of the individual activities implemented by SciLake partners, please consult the Continuous Reporting module of the Funding & Tenders Portal (sections: Dissemination, Communication Activities, Publications, and Datasets).

Table 2: Key performance indicators (KPIs) for SciLake communication and dissemination activities.

Activity	KPI
Website activity	8378 total users; 26k views (stats by Google Analytics)
SciLake Newsletter	Six issues; 47 subscribers, 50 extra views via webpage
SciLake printable material	100 fact sheets/cards distributed in external events; 31 downloads via webpage
SciLake branding	80 stickers distributed at external events
Participation in external events	40 events with contributions from SciLake partners
Pilot Press Release	Five press releases distributed via SciLake, OpenAIRE, HES-SO, EBRAINS, ICCS, CERTH, KI
Social media posts – X	280 posts; 177 followers
SciLake news article	40 news items
Publications	6 journal articles; 12 conference/workshop proceedings; 1 contribution to a periodic magazine
Datasets	5 OpenAIRE datasets for SciLake research pilots; 5 SKGs for SciLake research pilots; 1 BIP! dataset of Impact Measures for Research Products; 5 SKG-IF compliant OpenAIRE datasets for SciLake research pilots

Over time, our implementation evolved with respect to the D6.1 plan. We relied more on press releases and website news to highlight major milestones and publish stable updates that partners could easily reuse. At the same time, we moved away from video interviews and reduced our social media campaigns, instead prioritising fewer, more important messages amplified through partner channels and other initiatives with established audiences. We mainly focused on conferences and interactive formats such as talks, posters, workshops, and

panels, as these were the most effective ways to meet stakeholders in their “natural settings” and have direct conversations about the results, receiving valuable and constructive feedback.

Overall, the most effective channels were the project website, which served as a stable hub for results and reusable outputs, reinforced by partner and community amplification, and direct interaction through events and workshops. The least effective channels were general-purpose social media. A dedicated assessment of impact and contribution to project objectives is provided in Section 7.

5. Engagement activities

SciLake’s engagement work focused on demonstrating the value of SKGs through concrete pilot results, reaching target communities where they already meet, and creating a clear path from visibility to reuse by pointing stakeholders to tools and datasets. Opportunities were identified through ongoing monitoring of relevant calendars and networks, including EOSC and open science events, thematic conferences, and knowledge-management venues. Engagement was delivered through three main formats: conference contributions and booths (talks, papers, and posters at thematic conferences), workshops and interactive sessions to discuss interoperability choices and explore synergies with infrastructures and related projects, and online webinars to broaden reach and offer lower-barrier entry points for stakeholders across countries.

A full list of our participation in 40 external events is available on the website (<https://scilake.eu/news>). Table 3 highlights the events where we fostered engagement as organisers or co-organisers, focusing on major EOSC and open science events to maximise reach and support cross-project synergy. We also ran a smaller workshop co-located with a major transport research conference to collect practical feedback from pilot demonstrations.

Table 3: Key engagement events overview.

OSFAIR 2023 workshop on Open Science Knowledge Graphs (Sep 2023, Madrid)	
Format & SciLake role	Workshop session (organiser)
Main stakeholders	Service providers; Researchers; Research administrators
Outcome	Presented SciLake and introduced the “scientific lake” concept; discussed synergies with ESFRIs; collected community insights into the potential of SKGs.
	150 participants Summary: https://scilake.eu/open-science-knowledge-graphs-workshop Survey results: https://scilake.eu/survey-results-insights-into-the-potential-of-scientific-knowledge-graphs
SciLake plenary meetings (Nov 2023; Nov 2024)	
Format & SciLake role	Consortium coordination and open sessions (organiser)
Main stakeholders	Researchers; Service providers; Research administrators and policy makers; Impact assessment experts
Outcome	The plenary meetings provided opportunities to update consortium members and external stakeholders, and to position SciLake in the international landscape. The session “Towards Open Research Information” connected SciLake with the emerging Barcelona Declaration initiative (Barcelona, Nov 2023). The open sessions during the third plenary meeting connected SciLake with the Research Data Alliance working group on the SKG Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) and the EOSC ecosystem (Eindhoven, Nov 2024). 50 participants Summary: - https://scilake.eu/plenary2023

	- https://scilake.eu/scilake-third-plenary-meeting
EOSC-CoARA workshop for Advancing Research Assessment (Apr 2024, online)	
Format & SciLake role	Policy workshop (invited)
Main stakeholders	Impact assessment experts; Research administrators and policy makers
Outcome	Shared SciLake experience and inputs as an infrastructure for research assessment and alignment of EOSC and CoARA missions. Summary: https://scilake.eu/eosc-coara
EOSC Collaborative Frontiers to Achieve Interoperability and Enhance Scholarly Data (Oct 2024, Berlin)	
Format & SciLake role	Unconference session at EOSC Symposium (co-organised)
Main stakeholders	Service providers; Research administrators and policy makers
Outcome	The session deepened the EOSC community's understanding of SKG-IF and its real-world applications, created a space for productive dialogue about optimizing SKG-IF adoption, and gathered community feedback to help align future EOSC project efforts. 60 participants Summary: https://scilake.eu/scilake-at-eosc-symposium-2024 Presentations and Q&A report: https://zenodo.org/records/14290081
"Fairness & Transparency in Transport Research" workshop (Oct 2025, Thessaloniki)	
Format & SciLake role	Domain workshop (organiser)
Main stakeholders	Researchers; Research administrators and policy makers
Outcome	The event explored how FAIR principles can transform transport research through keynote presentations on Open Science and FAIR, live demos of SciLake tools applied to transport research pilots

	<p>(Maritime and CCAM), and interactive sessions that captured practical recommendations and follow-up needs.</p> <p>15 participants</p> <p>Summary: https://scilake.eu/ictr2025</p> <p>Workshop resources: https://zenodo.org/records/17481960</p>
<p>From fragments to insights: making scientific knowledge discoverable</p> <p>Results and opportunities from the SciLake project (Mar 2026, online)</p>	
Format & SciLake role	Project showcase + panels (organised)
Main stakeholders	Researchers; Service providers; Research administrators and policy makers; Impact assessment experts; General public
Outcome	<p>The final showcase of SciLake results and pilots demonstrated practical solutions to scientific knowledge fragmentation through customizable SKGs piloted in real-world, domain-specific contexts. The event included two panel discussions bringing together project partners and external experts from research infrastructures, policy, technology, and research communities. These discussions enabled cross-perspective dialogue on interoperability, sustainability, and adoption pathways.</p> <p>74 participants</p> <p>Summary: https://scilake.eu/closing-event</p>

Together, these engagement activities helped move SciLake from visibility to uptake by sharing and validating our narrative, engaging research assessment and policy actors who influence adoption decisions, and using pilot demonstrations to gather uptake signals and practical recommendations. A dedicated assessment of the impact of these activities and their contribution to project objectives is provided in Section 7.

5.1 Collaborations

SciLake worked with other INFRAEOSC projects and other international initiatives to share messages, align on interoperability work (including SKG-IF), and connect our results with related communities of open research information, research assessment, domain infrastructures, and research software quality. In practice, these synergies enabled coordinated engagement moments, alignment on SKG interoperability, and more efficient stakeholder outreach through a coherent cross-project narrative.

Table 4 summarises the main collaborations, their scope and the joint activities.

Table 4: *Collaborations overview (scope and joint activities).*

Partner/ initiative	Collaboration scope	Joint activities
OStrails	Interoperability and machine-actionable research workflows (planning–tracking–assessment); alignment with EOSC Interoperability Framework / RDA SKG-Interoperability; positioning SciLake within end-to-end workflow support.	Regular coordination and participation in each other’s initiatives; joint workshop “EOSC collaborative frontiers to achieve interoperability and enhance scholarly data” (EOSC Symposium 2024).
Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information	Alignment around open research information, knowledge discovery, and transparency in research assessment; reinforcing sustainability/governance narratives for open infrastructures.	Participation in DORI working groups; exchanges at Paris Conference (2024) and Bologna Meeting (2025); SciLake co-organised a Barcelona Declaration event in Athens (24 Nov 2025).
ECEMF (European Climate and Energy)	Energy-domain outreach channel; connecting SciLake’s energy pilot to the EU climate/energy modelling and policy community.	Coordinated promotion via websites and social channels; engagement during the ECEMF 2025 conference (Brussels).

Modelling Forum)		
EOSC4Cancer	Knowledge exchange on federated cancer data infrastructures, interoperability patterns, and analysis environments; alignment with/extension of cancer SKG models; positioning SciLake tools/services within the EOSC4Cancer ecosystem.	SciLake participation and monitoring of EOSC4Cancer activities; joint dissemination opportunities and mutual webinar invitations; SciLake participation in key events including “Defining the Roadmap for a European Cancer Data Space” (Brussels, Oct 2023) and Cancer Landscape Partnering meeting presentation (Feb 2024).
GraspOS	Assessment and indicators use cases; alignment on trustworthy, transparent metrics/indicators and the role of interoperable scholarly graphs; SKG-IF alignment and extensions.	Mutual monitoring and early access to deliverables; coordinated dissemination and joint events (including EOSC Symposium 2024 unconference session on SKG interoperability developments); joint press release (Apr 2024) recognising contributions to research assessment reform.
EVERSE	Research software and code excellence; adopting best practices for software quality.	Monitoring deliverables and exchanging practices; participation in shared events.

6. Exploitation strategy and plan

SciLake's exploitation activities focused on turning the project's results into assets that can be sustained and used beyond the grant's end. To make this work more structured and consistent across partners, the consortium participated in the Horizon Booster go-to-market (G2M) mentorship programme from February to July 2025. Horizon Booster provided a step-by-step method and templates to define the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs), agree on exploitation intentions for each partner, analyse the market/problem context, and translate the results into a practical exploitation strategy including a roadmap and a risk map.

The project identified two KERs:

1. **Scientific Lake Toolkit:** a bundle of open data, tools, and services from project partners to support domain knowledge management. All resources follow common interoperability standards to enable smooth integration and bundling, and the setup is designed to onboard additional providers that adhere to the same principles.
2. **SKG dataset collection:** five Scientific Knowledge Graph datasets, each focused on a specific domain (neuroscience, cancer, energy, maritime transport, and CCAM transport). The datasets support knowledge discovery and a range of research activities and applications.

The Horizon Booster work resulted in an exploitation strategy package comprising:

- (i) a characterisation of each result with scope, maturity, target users and customers, alternatives and competitors, and route to market;
- (ii) an exploitation roadmap with actions, responsibilities, and indicative timeline; and
- (iii) a map of key risks and mitigation measures.

The complete Horizon Booster process was finalised for KER 1 and is reported in Section 6.1 and Appendix A1. For KER 2, as the SKGs were finalised in the final phase of the project, the exploitation strategy was condensed into a shorter reflective assessment that drew on the Booster programme inputs, reported in Section 6.2 and Appendix A2.

6.1 KER1: Scientific Lake Toolkit

This KER provides a modular, openly accessible toolkit that bundles SciLake's core resources: open data, tools, and services that support communities in organising and using scientific knowledge more effectively. The toolkit aims to reduce fragmentation by enabling interoperable, reusable workflows for knowledge extraction, integration, discovery, impact analysis, and reproducibility-related use cases. It is designed as an extensible package: while SciLake partners are the initial contributors, the toolkit can onboard additional providers that follow the same interoperability principles.

The toolkit comprises 14 resources and is made available through the D4Science data catalogue (filter by Type "Tool"):

https://services.d4science.org/catalogue-d4s?path=/organization/scilake_lab

D4Science is a long-standing e-infrastructure in the European and international Open Science landscape, offering a stable and sustainable environment for the management, publication, and discovery of research resources. This ensures the persistence, availability, and long-term accessibility of the toolkit resources exposed via the catalogue.

The toolkit combines interoperable components built on knowledge graph technologies and related AI methods, enabling users to (i) extract and structure information from scholarly content, (ii) interlink and analyse knowledge graph content, and (iii) build value-added services for knowledge discovery, impact perspectives, and reproducibility-oriented assessment. By adhering to common interoperability standards, the toolkit supports seamless integration and bundling across components and can evolve as new tools and providers are added.

The exploitation strategy for KER1 was fully developed through the Horizon Booster go-to-market programme and is documented in the full set of Booster canvases and tables, reported in [Appendix A1](#):

- exploitation intention of the interested partners
- market definition canvas
- unique value proposition canvases for the three customer segments: researchers research administrators including impact evaluators, and builders/operators of SKGs
- exploitation strategy
- exploitation roadmap
- risk map.

The strategy focuses on keeping the toolkit components openly available via repositories (e.g., GitHub and partner infrastructures), maintaining them through institutional resources

complemented by new competitive funding, and supporting adoption through documentation, examples, and continued integration in operational services where relevant.

Overall, KER1's exploitation focuses on sustaining the toolkit as a reusable, interoperable "bundle" that can be adopted as individual components or as integrated packages, depending on user needs. The primary target context is scholarly communication and open science infrastructures, with key user groups including researchers, builders and operators of thematic or national SKGs, including EOSC providers, computer science communities working on graphs, AI, NLP, and standards, impact assessment experts, and research administrators. The main anticipated risks relate to long-term resourcing and maintenance, technology evolution (including rapid changes in AI methods), and the emergence of similar tools. Mitigation relies on modularity, continuous monitoring and adaptation, and embedding key components in established partner infrastructures.

6.2 KER2: SKG dataset collection

This KER delivers a curated, openly accessible collection of SKG datasets generated in SciLake's five pilot domains. The collection provides ready-to-reuse, interoperable graph representations of the scholarly record, intended to support experimentation, benchmarking, and downstream reuse by research communities, service providers, and EOSC-related initiatives. Each SKG is published on Zenodo with clear licensing and persistent identifiers, enabling citation and long-term access. The collection includes:

- SKG for Energy Planning Research: <https://zenodo.org/records/18470598>
- SKG for Cancer Research: <https://zenodo.org/records/18466321>
- SKG for Neuroscience Research: <https://zenodo.org/records/18471147>
- SKG for Maritime Transport Research: <https://zenodo.org/records/18548292>
- SKG for CCAM Transport Research: <https://zenodo.org/records/18548292>

Each graph is built using the OpenAIRE SKG-IF representation (e.g. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15855142>), which defines the core entities (Agents, Data sources, Grants, Products, Manifestations, Topics, and Venues), and is published on Zenodo under a CC-BY license. Enriched layers, including Fields of Science (FoS) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as Topic entities, as well as derived Research Artifacts and Citances, are computed with SciNoBo and released under a CC-BY-NC license. The full graph construction workflow is described in Section 4.5.1 of SciLake Deliverable 2.2 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18243603>).

As the SKGs were finalised in the final phase of the project, the exploitation strategy was condensed into a shorter reflective assessment that drew on the Booster programme inputs and was structured around the following aspects:

- Problem addressed
- Potential users
- Value and advantages
- Possible exploitation path
- Early adopters
- Challenges or risks
- Next steps after the project

Overall, KER2's exploitation focuses on keeping the SKG dataset collection openly available on Zenodo, and promoting it as a reusable, interoperable resource for research communities and supporting infrastructures. Across the five pilots, the aim is to discover research outputs that are fragmented and hard to find, by enabling semantic links, richer queries, and analytics across scholarly and domain entities. This can benefit researchers, research infrastructures and platform providers, policymakers and funders, and in some domains also industry (for example pharma and biotech, and ports and shipping). The preferred path is to integrate the collection within established open science infrastructures, especially OpenAIRE and EOSC-related services and domain gateways, supported by follow-up projects and community adoption that extend coverage and enrichments. Key risks include data quality and interoperability issues, such as heterogeneous sources, limits in automated extraction, and incomplete domain layers, as well as the effort needed for long-term maintenance and governance. Next steps therefore focus on widening the inputs, including full texts and more domain resources, and on building easier-to-use interfaces and visualisations, alongside targeted outreach to early adopters.

The detailed pilot-specific inputs underpinning these reflections are reported in the [Appendix A2](#).

7 Assessment of Communication, Engagement and Exploitation Activities

7.1 Assessment of impact and contribution to project objectives

The communication, engagement, and dissemination activities carried out throughout the project have established strong visibility for SciLake and positioned its results within relevant scientific and EOSC-related communities. Although the impact of such activities in research infrastructure projects is often gradual and extends beyond the project's duration, evidence from the reported KPIs shows that SciLake has successfully laid the foundations for further uptake and sustainability.

Website performance (8378 users and approximately 26000 views) demonstrates consistent interest from targeted audiences, particularly given the project's specialised nature. The website served as a central hub for accessing project results, including services, datasets, and case studies, supporting transparency and facilitating reuse. Continuous updates throughout the project lifecycle enabled stakeholders to follow the evolution of results and identify relevant entry points for engagement.

The production and dissemination of communication materials (including 40 news items, factsheets, and five pilot-specific press releases) helped maintain a coherent narrative and strengthen the project's visibility across multiple channels. Consortium partners actively amplified these materials through their own networks, particularly via established infrastructures such as OpenAIRE, significantly extending SciLake's reach beyond its core communication channels and ensuring alignment with broader open science initiatives.

Engagement through participation in 40 external events, as well as the organisation of workshops and webinars, was a key strength of the project's approach. These activities enabled direct interaction with stakeholders in their respective domains, facilitating not only awareness but also meaningful exchanges, feedback, and exploration of potential collaborations. Evidence from participation levels in selected events indicates that these formats were particularly effective in reaching expert communities and fostering dialogue around Scientific Knowledge Graphs and their applications.

In contrast, social media engagement (280 posts and 177 followers) was more limited, especially in the later stages of the project. However, this was proactively addressed through a

strategic shift towards more targeted and community-driven dissemination channels, which proved more effective for reaching specialised audiences. This adaptive approach demonstrates the project's ability to optimise its communication strategy in response to evolving conditions and maximise the impact of available resources.

Overall, SciLake has achieved its main communication and engagement objectives by: (i) raising awareness of Scientific Knowledge Graphs and their cross-domain potential, (ii) actively engaging key stakeholder groups through relevant and interactive formats, and (iii) ensuring open and structured access to project outputs. The project's integration within EOSC-related activities and collaborations with other INFRAEOSC initiatives further strengthens its positioning and enhances the potential for long-term uptake.

While direct measurement of uptake (e.g. sustained use of tools or integration into external systems) remains limited within the project timeframe, the combination of visibility, stakeholder engagement, and alignment with established infrastructures provides a strong basis for continued exploitation. In this respect, SciLake has effectively contributed to building awareness, trust, and initial adoption pathways, which are critical precursors to longer-term impact.

In conclusion, SciLake's communication and engagement activities have delivered a positive and measurable impact in terms of visibility, stakeholder interaction, and ecosystem positioning. By combining targeted dissemination, active engagement, and strategic alignment with EOSC, the project has created favourable conditions for the sustained use and further development of its results beyond the project's duration.

7.2 Risks, challenges, and mitigation measures in communication, engagement and exploitation

Throughout the implementation of communication and engagement activities, SciLake faced several challenges typical of research infrastructure projects operating in specialised scientific domains. These challenges were continuously monitored and, where necessary, addressed through adaptive strategies, contributing to the overall effectiveness of the Project's outreach.

A key challenge was the inherently specialised and technical nature of SciLake's results. SKGs and their associated services primarily target expert communities, which can limit the accessibility of messages to broader or non-technical audiences. To mitigate this, the project emphasised clear and consistent messaging, supported by visual materials (e.g. infographics, factsheets) and concrete pilot examples to illustrate the practical value of the approach. This improved understanding and relevance across different stakeholder groups.

Another challenge was the varying effectiveness of communication channels over time. In particular, engagement through general-purpose social media platforms proved less impactful than initially anticipated, especially in the later stages of the project. In response, SciLake adopted a more targeted dissemination strategy, prioritising established community channels (e.g. OpenAIRE networks, EOSC-related initiatives, and partner organisations) and direct interaction through events and workshops. This shift enabled the project to focus on higher-value engagement opportunities and reach audiences with a stronger interest in the project's results.

Engaging stakeholders beyond initial awareness towards active uptake also represents a broader structural challenge. While the project successfully reached and interacted with a wide range of stakeholders, the transition from engagement to sustained use of tools and services typically requires longer timeframes and continued support. To address this, SciLake emphasised open access to results (e.g. through repositories and the project website), alignment with EOSC initiatives, and participation in collaborative activities with related projects. These actions help lower barriers to adoption and facilitate continued use beyond the project duration.

Additionally, the diversity of stakeholder groups, ranging from researchers and infrastructure providers to policy actors, required tailored communication approaches. Ensuring consistent yet adaptable messaging across these audiences required continuous coordination within the consortium. This was effectively managed through a shared dissemination toolkit and an agreed core narrative, which supported coherence while allowing flexibility for domain-specific communication.

Overall, while these challenges influenced the implementation of communication and engagement activities, they were proactively addressed through adaptive and targeted measures. As a result, SciLake maintained effective outreach, optimised the use of communication channels, and strengthened its connection with relevant stakeholder communities. The experience gained provides valuable insights for future initiatives, particularly regarding the importance of targeted engagement strategies, flexible communication planning, and early alignment with user communities and infrastructures.

Appendix A1. Exploitation strategy for KER1: SciLake Toolkit

The tables and canvases in this section outline the core steps for defining a Key Exploitable Result and building the corresponding exploitation strategy.

A1.1 PARTNERS' EXPLOITATION INTENTIONS

All partners plan to maintain and further develop their components by integrating them into existing infrastructures and leveraging them in future research and service-oriented projects, relying on a mix of institutional funding and new competitive funding proposals.

Table A1.1: KER1 Exploitation intention

Partner	Exploitation intention	Organization's contribution to the generation of KER 1
ARC	ARC will sustain its toolkit resources through institutional funding and by securing new competitive funding opportunities.	ARC contributes to the following components of the toolbox: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lake API implementation - SciLake Knowledge Discovery Portals (BIP! Spaces) - BIP! Toolbox for multi-perspective impact analysis - SciNoBo Toolbox for entity extraction (RAA) & citation classification (Citance analysis) - SciNoBo Toolbox for Field of Science (FoS) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) classification - Automatic Machine Translation models - SciNeM (Data Science Tool for Heterogeneous Network Mining)
DFKI	DFKI is committed to maintaining the DSR tool and leveraging it to secure additional funding streams	DFKI: Document Structure Recognition tool (DSR)
OpenAIRE (with OpenAIRE members CNR and ICM)	OpenAIRE will integrate the Information Inference Service and PDF Fetcher into their Sustainability plan, while exposing the toolkit catalogue through the	OpenAIRE: Toolkit catalogue, Information Inference Service, PDF Fetcher

	D4Science infrastructure	
Opix	OPIX will ensure long-term sustainability through internal funding, with plans to expand its analytical capabilities into additional domains to increase impact.	OPIX: Classification tools, Reproducibility assistant tools. Language detection on scientific articles. Technology extraction in publications for Energy, Cancer, Neuroscience and Transport domains
SIRIS	SIRIS will maintain its toolkit resources through secured institutional funding.	SIRIS: Entity recognition
TUe	TU/e plans to maintain and enhance its toolkit contributions through a combination of institutional support and competitive funding.	TU/e contributes the following components to the Scientific Lake Toolkit: (1) tools for storing, querying, and extracting insights from interconnected scientific information, powered by AvantGraph database (avantgraph.io), supporting operations from upstream applications; (2) Well-documented interfaces for accessing and manipulating scientific data (APIs)

A1.2 MARKET DEFINITION CANVAS

The canvas in Figure A1.2 clarifies the market context: scientific and scholarly content is increasingly open and accessible, but it delivers tangible value only when it is organised and made interoperable.

We identified three primary user categories ("job executors"):

- Researchers
- Research administrators (including impact evaluators)
- Builders/operators of Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs)

Within this context, the Scientific Lake toolkit functions as a modular bundle of open data, tools, and services that helps users organise and use scientific knowledge more effectively. By adhering to common interoperability standards, the toolkit supports easier integration and bundling of components, enabling workflows that improve discovery, data access, reproducibility-oriented use cases, and other research-related activities.

The canvas also highlights how the toolkit compares with alternative solutions:

- The modular architecture allows users to select individual components or adopt integrated packages depending on their needs, while keeping the ecosystem extensible for additional tools and services.
- In contrast to many sector-specific solutions, SciLake combines technical expertise with domain-informed insights from researchers across different disciplines.

Finally, the canvas summarises the main need as:

- Abstracted job statement: organise knowledge so it can be easily utilised in day-to-day work and support effective outcomes.
- Job-to-be-done: utilise openly available knowledge in a structured way.

Figure A1.2: KER1 Market definition canvas

A1.3 UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION

Following the market analysis, we define KER1's unique value proposition for each user category. The canvases below show how the SciLake toolkit creates value by delivering measurable gains and addressing key pain points for researchers, research administrators, and builders and operators of Scientific Knowledge Graphs.

Figures A1.3.1-A1.3.3 display the benefits, such as reduced time for processing and analysing scholarly content, and improved discoverability and interoperability. Compared with fragmented point solutions, SciLake provides a unified and interoperable approach.

The Value Proposition Canvas SciLake

Customer Segment: **Researchers** creating, managing, accessing, and processing scholarly content to enhance the visibility and value of research outputs.

Figure A1.3.1: KER 1 value proposition for researchers.

The Value Proposition Canvas

Customer Segment: **Research Administrator, including Impact Evaluators**

Figure A1.3.2: KER 1 value proposition for research administrators.

The Value Proposition Canvas

Customer Segment: **Builders/operators of Scientific Knowledge Graphs**

Figure A1.3.3: KER 1 value proposition for builders and operators of SKGs.

A1.4 EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

Table A1.4: KER 1 Exploitation strategy

KER Description	<p>The toolkit combines resources (open data, tools, and services) to help researchers better organize and use scientific knowledge, simplify data access, improve discovery, reproducibility, and other research-related activities. All resources adhere to common interoperability standards, enabling seamless integration and bundling. Though project partners are currently the primary contributors, the toolkit is designed to welcome additional providers who adhere to the same interoperability principles. This makes the toolkit particularly suitable for integration into research infrastructures and data platforms requiring scalable and interoperable solutions.</p>
Target market/end users	<p><i>target market:</i> Research infrastructures, scholarly communication platforms, and organisations managing large-scale scientific data and knowledge</p> <p><i>customers/end-users:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers: Receive support in creating, managing, accessing, and processing scholarly content to enhance the visibility and value of research outputs. - Builders and operators of thematic or national Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs): Receive tools to improve the interlinking of SKGs and scholarly content. - Computer Science Communities: Receive tools to improve the quality of SKGs in terms of disambiguation, enrichment, and functionalities for impact and reproducibility assessment. - Impact assessment experts: Can analyze research impact through multiple perspectives and conduct more transparent evaluations using openly available data and tools. - Research administrators: Gain support in identifying research trends and evaluating the reproducibility of research outputs.
Market drivers	<p>These features respond to the growing need for interoperable, scalable, and domain-adaptable solutions in open science and EOSC-related infrastructures.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Comprehensive and flexible deployment: The toolkit's modular architecture allows users to select components based on their specific needs, from individual tools to fully integrated packages, offering greater flexibility. Moreover, by adhering to common interoperability standards, the toolkit facilitates easier integration of new tools and services, creating an expandable ecosystem that can evolve with research needs. - Cross-Domain Adaptability: Most existing tools are sector-specific, whereas SciLake combines the expertise of technical specialists with the domain-specific insights of researchers from diverse fields.
Use model	<p>The toolkit is delivered under an open-source model and made accessible through open repositories (e.g., GitHub) and partner infrastructures, supported by integration into established service ecosystems. This enables two complementary modes of use:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct adoption by research teams, who can freely discover, download, and run individual components or compose them into workflows.

	<p>- Deployment within larger infrastructures, where operators can integrate and bundle components as part of interoperable services for knowledge extraction, integration, discovery, impact analysis, and reproducibility-oriented use cases. Sustained availability is ensured through institutional maintenance complemented by competitive funding, while documentation and worked examples support implementation and uptake. Components are made available under CC-BY licensing to encourage reuse across providers.</p>
Early Adopters	<p>Early adopters include research infrastructures (e.g. EOSC-related initiatives), interdisciplinary research groups, and organisations managing large-scale scholarly data collections.</p>
Adopters' problems/needs	<p>For example, interdisciplinary research teams that need to integrate diverse sources of knowledge and organizations that need to extract insights from complex scientific literature for decision-making purposes.</p>
Alternative solution	<p>Current solutions include commercial scholarly analytics platforms, domain-specific tools, and fragmented open-source solutions, which often lack interoperability, transparency, or flexibility.</p>
Unique Value Proposition	<p>Our UVP consists of 3 key features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple Components <p>SciLake provides a set of interconnected tools built on knowledge graph technology, facilitating efficient scientific information extraction and analysis.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy Implementation <p>The ecosystem can be readily deployed on a computer cluster. Researchers can selectively install and utilize components that align with their specific requirements, whether opting for individual tools or integrated packages.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptability <p>The flexible framework allows researchers across various disciplines to customize SciLake for their unique projects, as demonstrated by our pilot programs, making it an invaluable asset for diverse scientific endeavors.</p>
Competitors	<p>Competitors include analytics platforms that provide large-scale access to scholarly data but often lack the modularity, interoperability standards, and domain-specific adaptability that SciLake offers. SciLake differentiates itself by enabling flexible tool integration and supporting community-driven knowledge graph creation across multiple domains.</p>
Timing	<p>The toolkit reached initial maturity in March 2026 and is expected to evolve further through post-project activities and integration into existing infrastructures</p>
IPR	<p>The Consortium Agreement and Grant Agreement regulate the ownership of results: "Results are owned by the Party (the beneficiary organisation or associated partner) that generates them."</p> <p>For joint results, no specific written agreements of this kind have been created.</p>

A1.5 EXPLOITATION ROADMAP

Table A1.5: KER1 Exploitation roadmap

Exploitation roadmap for KER: Scientific Lake Toolkit	
Actions Actions include maintenance of key components, documentation and technical enhancements, and domain expansion.	ATHENA RC: Maintenance and bug fixing for Lake API implementation; ensuring API deployment and BIP! Spaces remain accessible to pilot partners for at least two years, attracting new clients for BIP!Spaces; improving platform features based on user feedback; maintaining and updating other components (BIP! Toolbox, SciNoBo Toolbox, etc.).
	DFKI: Finalizing documentation and user guides to maintain the DSR tool and leverage it for new funding opportunities.
	OpenAIRE, CNR, ICM: No additional activities required as services are already integrated into the OpenAIRE infrastructure (IIS and PDF fetcher) and will continue to run; the toolkit catalogue is hosted by D4Science with no maintenance issues.
	Opix: No additional work needed for extracted technology mentions; maintenance and technical work focused on language detection tools; extending analysis to other domains.
	SIRIS: Consolidation of entity extraction for project pilots; polishing pipeline to simplify adaptability to new domains; creating well-defined and documented templates within 6 months of project conclusion.
	TU/e: Consolidate technical work and finalise user guides.
Roles	Roles follow the contributions described in the exploitation intentions table A1.1, with each partner responsible for maintaining and developing their respective components.
Milestones	ATHENA RC has established clear targets including maintaining the Lake API deployment for a minimum of two years after project completion, creating at least 5 BIP! Spaces outside the original SciLake pilots, and committing to at least 3 new dataset releases annually for the BIP! Toolbox.

	SIRIS has committed to developing a well-defined and documented template within six months of the project conclusion to improve domain adaptability. The remaining partners (DFKI, OpenAIRE/CNR/ICM, Opix, and TU/e) have not identified specific milestones beyond routine maintenance work for their respective components, as many of their contributions are already integrated into existing infrastructures or require minimal post-project intervention.
Costs	Most partners will rely primarily on institutional funding to support their post-project activities. No specific costs have been identified as the maintenance activities require no additional investments beyond ordinary research processes (no investments, patents, etc.).
Revenues	No direct revenue streams are currently defined, as the toolkit follows an open-source and infrastructure-oriented model. However, indirect value is generated through integration into funded projects, service provision, and contribution to research infrastructures.
Other sources of coverage	Partners will fund post-project activities primarily through institutional resources, and in some cases pursue competitive funding opportunities to support tool extensions.

A1.6 RISK MAP

Table A1.6: KER 1 Risk Assessment Map

Risks	Criticality	Probability	Risk Grade	Potential intervention	Feasibility	Conclusion
Partnership Risk Factors						
Partner leaves	3	3	9	Meetings	3	No Action
Technological Risk Factors						
Because of AI the technology becomes obsolete	8	5	40	Hybrid solutions for better leverage. Traditional approaches and AI-based ones	8	Control.
Market Risk Factors						
Similar more efficient	8	5	40	Follow up on similar	7	Control.

tools				projects and adapt		
IPR/Legal Risk Factors						
Need for expensive Licensing for some components	8	5	40	Freedom to operate analysis	3	No Action

Dependency on non-open IP	5	3	15	Freedom to operate analysis	6	Control.
Financial/Management Risk Factors						
Athena RC: Unable to attract new competitive funding.	7	7	49	Use institutional funding (i.e., internal projects using overheads from other R&D activities) and keep extensions to a minimum. Exploit volunteer programmers' efforts (all code is open source), leveraging connections with universities and the option to use students for dissertations and internships.	7	Control.
SIRIS: Lack of human resources	3	8	24	Set up an internal R&D project	5	Between Control & No Action
Environmental/Regulation/Safety risks:						
Energy expenditure	8	7	56	Optimise code. Provide energy usage data	5	Between Action & Warning

Appendix A2. Exploitation Strategy for KER2: SKG dataset collection

The table below summarises, for each pilot domain, the key elements of the exploitation reflection: the problem addressed, potential users, value and advantages, possible exploitation paths, early adopters, challenges/risks, and next steps. Together, they provide a comparable snapshot of where the SKG dataset collection can create value and what would be needed to sustain and grow its reuse after the project.

Problem Addressed: What problem or need does this result address?	
Energy	<p>Energy research outputs are widely distributed across repositories and lack structured geographic information about where studies are conducted. This creates several limitations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - difficulty identifying regional research activity and thematic concentration, - limited capacity to analyse territorial patterns of research, - challenges in linking scientific knowledge with regional energy policies or planning needs, - limited discoverability of geographically relevant research outputs. <p>The SciLake SKG addresses this gap by making outputs related to regional energy planning easily discoverable.</p>
Cancer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration of heterogeneous biomedical data into a unified resource - Exploration of complex relationships in CLL and cancer biology - Translation of biological questions into structured queries - Fragmentation of cancer knowledge across multiple sources - Limited support for multi-omics and systems-level analysis - Identification of relevant and high-impact scientific literature - Lack of reusable, ML-ready knowledge structures
Neuroscience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fragmented scientific knowledge - Limited discoverability
Maritime Transport	<p>(i) Existing maritime datasets and publications are often stored in heterogeneous formats and systems, lacking common standards and semantic links, which hinders integration and reuse. (ii) Researchers and practitioners face challenges connecting related concepts, datasets, and findings, limiting evidence-based decision-making in maritime transport.</p>

CCAM Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research outputs remain difficult to be discovered - Difficulty in interconnecting resources (datasets) with scientific results
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Potential Users: Who could benefit from this result after the project?

Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - energy researchers studying regional energy systems - research infrastructures and repositories managing scientific publications - policy analysts and policymakers assessing research landscapes and innovation capacity - European research projects working on energy transition topics - Regional innovation and planning stakeholders are interested in territorial knowledge about energy research.
Cancer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biomedical and cancer researchers (e.g. oncology, molecular biology, bioinformatics) - Research infrastructures and data platform providers - Pharmaceutical and biotechnology companies - Clinical researchers and precision medicine stakeholders - AI/ML researchers working on biomedical data analysis
Neuroscience	<p>Researchers; Funding agencies; Publishers</p>
Maritime Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maritime researchers and academics, - Port authorities and maritime operators, - Policymakers and regulatory bodies, - Industry stakeholders (e.g. shipping companies, logistics providers), - Data scientists and technology developers
CCAM Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers from Transport Institutes or Academia - Researchers from Original Equipment Manufacturers - CCAM pilot integrators - CCAM service orchestrators - PDI (Physical Digital Infrastructure) operators - Standardization bodies

Value and Advantages: What are the main benefits compared to existing solutions or current practices?

Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved discoverability of geographically relevant research outputs - Ability to perform spatial analysis of scientific research activity - Integration of heterogeneous research metadata into a unified knowledge graph - Support for advanced queries and analytics through graph technologies - Automated processing that reduces the need for manual geographic tagging
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	<p>of publications.</p> <p>The SKG enables new analytical perspectives, such as comparing research activity with regional energy potential or infrastructure deployment</p>
Cancer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unified integration of multi-source biomedical data into a single knowledge graph - Improved discovery of relationships across genes, proteins, diseases, drugs, and literature - Faster and more efficient querying of complex biological questions - Support for advanced graph analytics and hypothesis generation - ML-ready structure enabling reuse in downstream analytical workflows
Neuroscience	<p>Brings together Datasets and Publications in one place</p> <p>Interlinks the research outputs with domain-specific entities, improving knowledge discovery</p> <p>Ability to perform queries and analytics on the SKG</p>
Maritime Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enables semantic search and linking of maritime research outputs, surpassing the keyword-based retrieval used in traditional repositories. - Integrates heterogeneous data sources (publications, datasets, metadata) through common ontologies and standards. - Transforms unstructured information into interconnected SKGs, facilitating automated analysis and reuse. - Connects maritime knowledge with related domains (e.g. environment, logistics, transport), which is rarely supported in current isolated systems. - Allows users to navigate relationships between concepts, datasets, and findings, reducing time and effort in literature and data review. - Provides a foundation for data-driven tools, decision support systems, and intelligent applications not feasible with fragmented data sources. - Promotes FAIR data practices, improving transparency and reuse of maritime research outputs.
CCAM Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved discoverability of research outputs - Application of complex queries upon the SKG providing results that would not be feasible in a conventional way - Identification of scientific interconnected links among CCAM graph nodes

Possible Exploitation Path: How could this result be used or maintained after the project?

Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - integration into existing research infrastructures such as OpenAIRE or other SKGs - further development within future EU-funded research projects focusing on energy transition or science analytics - deployment as an open-source workflow for enriching research metadata
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	<p>with geographic information</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - operation as a service supporting research landscape analysis provided by participating institutions.
Cancer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration into existing biomedical research infrastructures and platforms - Extension with additional cancer datasets and multi-omics data - Use as a foundation for ML/AI-driven precision oncology applications - Further development through follow-up research projects - Maintenance and evolution via partner institutions or open-source contributions
Neuroscience	<p>maintain the OpenAIRE neuroscience gateway</p>
Maritime Transport	<p>The Maritime SKGs developed under KER2 can continue to be used and maintained beyond the project by integrating them into existing research infrastructures and open science platforms, ensuring accessibility to a wider community of users. They can be regularly enriched with new publications, datasets, and metadata through automated data pipelines and contributions from relevant stakeholders, such as research institutions and port authorities. In addition, the SKGs can serve as a foundation for ongoing analytics, decision-support tools, and AI-based applications in the maritime domain. Their long-term sustainability can be supported through adoption by partner organisations or other relevant initiatives, accompanied by clear governance mechanisms for data curation and quality assurance. Furthermore, the SKGs can be extended to cover additional domains and use cases, facilitating cross-domain knowledge sharing and enhancing their overall value over time.</p>
CCAM Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Further development through EU co-funded research projects - Integration on existing research infrastructures, services and procedures, like OpenAIRE - Internal agreement between project partners to unofficial test any technical advancements on a bilateral win-win basis

Early Adopters: Which organisations or communities might be interested in adopting this result first?

Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - energy research communities studying renewable energy systems - European research infrastructures such as OpenAIRE and EOSC-related services - EU research projects analysing energy transition dynamics - organisations involved in science policy, research evaluation, or innovation monitoring.
Cancer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cancer research and bioinformatics communities (e.g. CLL and systems

	<p>oncology)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - European biomedical research infrastructures (e.g. ELIXIR nodes) - New EU-funded projects in cancer, AI, and data-driven health - Pharmaceutical and biotech R&D communities
Neuroscience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Neuroscience researchers would be interested in finding all relevant research in one place - Neuroscience repositories and journals might be interested in impact indicators for their content - Funding organisations and Publishers might be interested in knowing if sharing data makes research more impactful
Maritime Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research organisations and universities engaged in maritime transport and logistics studies. - Port authorities and port management organisations seeking data-driven insights. - Maritime industry stakeholders, including shipping companies, logistics providers, and maritime technology firms. - Open science and research infrastructure initiatives. - Public authorities and policy bodies involved in maritime transport and sustainability.
CCAM Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CCAM related research communities - ITS and C-ITS related organizations - Standardization bodies dealing on recent CCAM related trends/subjects

Challenges or Risks: What factors might limit or slow down the exploitation of this result?

Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the precision of automated geographic extraction (currently around 70–80%), missing interface / platform that does not require coding / downloadable results - the need to improve the filtering of energy-related publications within the OpenAIRE dataset - technical maintenance requirements for the knowledge graph infrastructure - integration challenges with existing research infrastructures - the need to increase awareness and usability among potential user communities despite the lack of a user-friendly service
Cancer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited maturity due to short evaluation and testing period - Integration challenges with external biomedical data sources and standards - Need for continuous updates and maintenance of multi-omics data - Dependence on domain-specific expertise for effective use

Neuroscience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OpenAIRE gateway does not include all the neuroscience repositories and journals out there. It needs to be improved and maintained - Only a few domain-specific entities exist in the SKG at the moment - Author impact cannot be assessed in the current SKG - Results for the citation counts need to be verified
Maritime Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Heterogeneity in data formats, metadata, and ontologies across sources may hinder full interoperability. - Ongoing curation, updates, and governance require dedicated resources and long-term commitment. - Difficulty in aligning SKGs with legacy IT systems and workflows in different organisations.
CCAM Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Missing funding for maintenance/upgrade - Difficulty in effectively interconnecting scientific resources during the integration process - Limited interest from potential stakeholders due to poor dissemination or incompatible prioritization

Next Steps After the Project: What actions would be needed to further develop or deploy this result?

Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improving entity extraction models and precision through additional training and validation - expanding the workflow to process full-text publications rather than titles and abstracts only - refining the energy corpus filtering to reduce domain noise - developing user-friendly interfaces and visualization tools for non-technical users - integrating the workflow with European research infrastructures and EOSC services.
Cancer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Further technical development and optimisation of the knowledge graph - Integration with additional biomedical platforms and data sources - Expansion with new multi-omics and clinical datasets - Community engagement with cancer research and bioinformatics users
Neuroscience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration of more domain specific entities from resources such as openMINDS - Running Named Entity Recognition on full texts - Recommending communities to follow correct citation practices for datasets and to add ORCID IDs to authors while publishing
Maritime Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate additional maritime datasets, publications, and real-time data sources to enhance coverage and value.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Further develop and adopt common ontologies, metadata standards, and interoperability frameworks.- Engage with ports, industry stakeholders, and research infrastructures to support adoption and co-development.
CCAM Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Upgrade of the data model used- Enhancement of the scientific resources used as reference- Additional funding- Integration into EU policies and promotion from relative services